

8T – The Coupling Constants Series, SSB and Neutrino Effective Mass

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Abstract:

Following the previous paper regarding the Neutrino masses propagating alongside the electron and do not effecting the coupling term, author will argue for the idea of effective mass. The photon has an effective mass, as it is an energy carrier. The electron Neutrino massless term in the coupling is ensuring the coupling term does not vary, however It is known that the Neutrino is a mass carrier. Author will argue it is a mass of the effective kind, similar to the photon.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. From experiment, we know that the electron does not propagate by itself but rather with another ghost particle, the electron neutrino. What kind of numerical traits in the 8T this particle possess? In other words, we need to add it the coupling term (1.44) without changing the magnitude of the coupling. If reader is familiar with the 8T two symmetry breaking – inward to generate mass:

$$8 - (1)$$

Moreover, outward to generate a ripple on the matric tensor given by the term:

$$8 + (1)$$

The answer is clear the ghost particle, the electron neutrino cannot be associated with neither symmetry breaking classes. It has the be a particle which has no effect on the coupling term, we can represent it but it will vanish. The answer than is that the electron neutrino is represented by the following numerical trait that associate with vanishing in the 8T:

$$v_e \rightarrow 8n ;$$

$$n \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + 8 + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + v_e + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.47)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + v_e + (e)] + \gamma = 128 \quad (1.48)$$

$$v_e = 0$$

$$[(24 * 5) + \nu_e + (e)] + \gamma \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \quad (1.49)$$

In previous paper, it was mentioned by the author that the Neutrino is massless. However, in this paper, author will emphasize that statement as modern physics predict that the Neutrino has mass. If it had mass of the kind that is converging to a point, then the third and second coupling term would not be correct. Since it is vanishing, it is unclear why such particle appears in the first place. Author would like to coin a new term in 8T – **Effective mass**. The photon is massless; at the same time, it has effective mass as it can exert pressure diverging and similarly the Neutrino.

Effective mass is raw energy, curvature diverging, similar to the photon. That is supported by the famous equation on energy and mass. So even massless particles, which are bosons, can exert pressure on tiny scales on the metric tensor M , which will be equivalent to a mass effect. The emphasis of that point is important as we are facing a challenge. How to retain the finite and seemingly invariant coupling terms, if the Neutrino has a non-vanishing mass due to SSB of the second kind. The answer is simple, and that is to assume it has energy. The mass of the Neutrino is a form of energy. Taken from that point of view it is possible to reason why it is so difficult to detect such interactions between fermions and those Neutrinos, that is because they are manifested in a vanishing symmetry, raw variation, the coupling term is the same with or without the Neutrino.

It is also impossible (to date) to estimate the actual mass of the Neutrino nor its additional features. In complete contrast to the 8T mathematical extrapolation of the coupling series, the Neutrino was added because of modern physical measurement and without it, the term would not be included. The key point to take from this, is that massless in one way, does not mean massless in another. There are two distinct kinds of SSB and natural elements that can be regarded to either SSB, by requiring it will have energy. Another way to state it, is that the Neutrino has a perfect symmetry, and infinitesimal amount of energy.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)